

VISIONS OF MEANING FOR IMPACT-ORIENTED INFORMATION SYSTEMS RESEARCH IN TIMES OF POLYCRISIS: QUO VADIS?

Submission Instructions

Overview of Submission Requirements

Before submitting, ensure that your contribution meets the workshop requirements:

- **Length:** Up to 6 pages (including references)
- **Format:** PDF
- **Template:** ECIS template (Debate & Provocation style)
- **Content:** Reflective, well-argued contribution between a position statement and research
- **Author information:** Must be included in the submitted PDF

Submissions are handled via Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/iis-workshop/>

An active Zenodo account is required.

Step 1: Create or Log Into Your Zenodo Account

1. Go to <https://zenodo.org>
2. Click “**Log in**” (top right corner)
3. Choose one of the login options:
 - ORCID (recommended)
 - GitHub
 - Email/password

If you do not have an account:

- Click “**Sign up**” and follow the registration steps

Step 2: Access the IIS Workshop Community

1. Open the community page: <https://zenodo.org/communities/iis-workshop/>
2. Click the “**Upload**” or “**New upload**” button
 - This will take you to the Zenodo submission form

Step 3: Upload Your Submission File

1. In the upload interface:
 - Drag and drop your PDF file OR
 - Click “**Choose files**” and select your document
2. Wait until the upload completes successfully

Step 4: Fill in Metadata

Zenodo will ask for metadata. For this workshop, only basic fields are required:

Required Fields

- **Title:** Your paper title
- **Authors:** Add all authors
- **Description:** Brief abstract or summary of your contribution
- **Upload type:** Select “**Publication**” → “Conference paper”

Step 5: Assign to the IIS Workshop Community

This is a **critical step**. Ensure that the submission is assigned to the right community.

1. Scroll to the “**Communities**” section
2. Search for: “**iis-workshop**”
3. Select the community
4. Click “**Add**”

Your submission must be linked to the correct community to be considered for review.

Step 6: Save and Publish Your Submission

1. Click “**Save**” to review your entry
2. Carefully check:
 - File uploaded correctly
 - Metadata is accurate
 - Community is selected
3. Click “**Publish**”
4. Confirm publication when prompted

Step 7: After Submission

- Your submission will be visible in Zenodo
- The workshop organizers will review it via the community

- Feedback will be provided on a rolling basis
- After the review process is completed, the submission will automatically be added to the Zenodo Community

Key dates:

- Initial submission deadline: **May 15, 2026**
- Feedback: Rolling until **May 22, 2026**
- Final submission deadline: **May 29, 2026**

Contact

For questions regarding the workshop: iis-workshop@proton.me